

Analysis of Product Quality, Brand Image and after Sales Services toward Purchase Decisions and Customer Satisfaction (Case Study of Indramayu Marketplace)

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine and analyze the effect of product quality, brand image, and after-sales service on purchasing decisions and the impact on customer satisfaction of Toyota cars in the Indramayu Regency. The population in this study is the people of Indramayu Regency who have Toyota cars, with a sample of 172 respondents. The data analysis method used Structural Equation Model – Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS). The results in this study that product quality has a positive and significant impact on Toyota car purchasing decisions. Brand image, after-sales service, Purchase decisions positively and significantly impact customer satisfaction for Toyota cars. Product quality and Brand image have a significant influence on customer satisfaction. Therefore, after-sales service, Product quality also positively impacts customer satisfaction mediated purchasing decisions. Brand image affects customer satisfaction mediated purchasing

decisions. After-sales service has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction mediated purchasing decisions.

Keywords:- Product Quality, Brand Image, After Sales Service, Purchase Decision, Customer Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Advances in technology are currently experiencing reasonably rapid development so that it will encourage the pace of development of the business world to be more rapid and competition to be more competitive. Technology in the car industry is also experiencing rapid development, so more products will be offered to meet consumer needs, but car sales development is not following technological advances in the car industry. Therefore, Figure 1 Car sales in Indonesia have fluctuated in sales over the last four years.

Fig. 1: Car Sales in Indonesia Year 2016-2019

Sources: Gaikindo

Judging from the data in Figure 1, car sales in Indonesia in the last four years, namely from 2016 to 2019, reached 4,321,492 units. In 2016 car sales were 1,062,694 units. In 2017 car sales were 1,077,364 units. This number has increased from the previous year, which was 14,670 units. In 2018 car sales were 1,151,308 units. This number increased from the previous year, which was 73,944 units. In 2019 car sales were 1,030,126 units. This number experienced a decrease in car sales from the previous year, 121,182 units.

According to Gaikindo (Indonesian Automotive Industry Association), the decline in car sales in 2019 was due to the election, so many people were delaying buying a car. The number of car sales that have changed in the last four years has made competition in the Indonesian automotive industry increasingly fierce so that each car manufacturer puts out all of its capabilities to create a product that suits the needs and desires of consumers.

Toyota is one of the manufacturers in the competition for the Indonesian car automotive industry; among the many competing car manufacturers in Indonesia, ten car

manufacturers have the highest sales in the 2016 to 2019 period, according to the Indonesian Automotive Industry Association (GAIKINDO), which can see in table 1.

No.	Brand	Total Sales
1	Toyota	1,758,678 Unit
2	Daihatsu	923,894 Unit
3	Honda	844,978 Unit
4	Suzuki	544,812 Unit
5	Mitsubishi	520,649 Unit
6	Isuzu	107,651 Unit
7	Daihatsu	82,245Unit
8	Nissan	71,936 Unit
9	Wuling	44,395 Unit
10	Mazda	28,404 Unit

Table 1: Top 10 automotive brands in Indonesia

Sources: Gaikindo

PT. Toyota Astra Motor is the sole agent for the Toyota brand in Indonesia; Toyota has several types of cars marketed in Indonesia, with many types of cars owned by Toyota, making consumers have many choices, so consumers can choose the type of car that suits their needs. Several types of cars are marketed in Indonesia, namely: Hatchback types, namely Agya and Yaris. MVP types, namely Alphard, Vellfire, Calya, Avanza, Veloz, Kijang Innova, Sienta, and Voxy. Sedan types, namely Corolla Altis, Camry, and Vios. There are types of SUVs, namely

Fortuner, Corolla Cross, Rush, C-HR, and Land Cruiser. Hybrid types, namely Corolla Cross Hybrid, Corolla Altis Hybrid, C-HR Hybrid, Camry Hybrid. Commercial types, namely Hilux D Cab, Dyna, HiAce, and Hilux S Cab. Type of Sport, namely Toyota 86 and Toyota GR Supra. In addition, Toyota also has good after-sales service, proven by Toyota having dealers and workshops spread throughout Indonesia. Toyota's sales from 2016 to 2019 can check in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Toyota Sales Data for 2016 – 2019

Sumber: Gaikindo

Toyota has carried out various strategies to win the competition. The strategy that Toyota carried out is by creating innovations in its products both in terms of the car exterior and interior models and technology. Can get products from Toyota quickly, in addition to getting products from Toyota, dealers also function as a place for after-sales service so that customers get maximum service after purchasing the car, so this Toyota car is very popular with consumers in Indramayu Regency.

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Product quality is one of the purchasing decision factors; according to Tumembouw et al. (2019), product quality influences purchasing decisions. So that good product quality is product quality that can meet the needs and desires of consumers. Quality is the totality of features and characteristics of a product or service that depend on its ability to satisfy implied needs. Product quality is the ability of a product to perform its function, and this includes overall

durability, reliability, accuracy, ease of operation, product repair, and other attributes (Kotler and Keller, 2016).

Brand image is a set of beliefs trusted by consumers for a particular brand (Kotler and Armstrong, 2008). Brand image is one of the purchasing decision factors; according to Joghee & Dube (2018), brand image influences customer satisfaction. So that a good brand image is a brand image established by the company with consumer confidence in certain products with the quality and benefits of the products offered so that when consumers use these products can feel the benefits of the brand such as self-confidence and pride, then the brand image can influence the consumer's decision to buy a car.

Djohan and Adhani (2016) state that producers provide after-sales service to consumers after buying products from the company. After-sales service is one of the purchasing decision factors. According to Mohan et al. (2018), sales significantly influence purchasing decisions. After-sales service guarantees that the product that was purchased is damaged. It can be repaired at an official workshop or refunded by the consumer. Besides that, the company also provides workshops in every area so that it is easy to reach if one day the product has been purchased by consumers damaged, as well as equipping spare parts in all authorized workshops, in order to speed up the repair of damaged products if there are spare parts that replaced without having to wait long for spare parts delivery from the central workshop. So after-sales service like this can affect consumer decisions in buying a car.

According to Tjiptono and Chandra (2017), Purchase decisions are part of the consumer decision-making process, while according to Kotler and Keller (2012), purchasing decisions are actions from consumers to want to buy or not to a product. Based on several understandings of purchasing decisions above, the researcher concludes that purchasing decisions are consumer attitudes towards certain products so that consumers decide to make a purchase or not.

According to Tjiptono and Chandra (2017), consumer satisfaction and dissatisfaction impact the comparison between consumer expectations before purchase and actual product performance. When buying a product, consumers

have expectations about how the product will perform. According to Kotler and Keller (2016), customer satisfaction is the level of one's feelings after comparing the product performance with his expectations. Based on the notion of customer satisfaction described above, the researcher concludes that consumer satisfaction is an expectation from consumers of the purchased product. If the product performs better than expected, the consumer will feel satisfied.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Type of Research Design

This research uses quantitative methods; according to Sugiyono (2017), quantitative methods are often referred to as positivistic methods because it on the philosophy of positivism. This method is a scientific/scientific method because it has complied with scientific principles, namely concrete/empirical, objective, measurable, rational, and systematic. Use the quantitative method because the research data is in numbers, and the analysis uses statistics. They are used to research a particular population or sample, data collection using research instruments, quantitative or statistical data analysis to test predetermined hypotheses. The population in this study is the people of Indramayu Regency who have Toyota brand cars.

In this study, the data process using the partial least square (PLS) method using the SmartPLS version 3.0 software program. PLS (Partial Least Square) is an alternative model of covariance-based SEM. PLS intend for causal predictive analysis in the high complexity and low theoretical support (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). According to Ghozali & Latan (2015), PLS aims to help researchers get the value of latent variables for prediction purposes. The latent variable is the linear aggregate of the indicators. The weight estimate for creating the component score for the latent variable is obtained based on how the inner model (structural model that links latent variables) and the outer model (measurement model, namely the relationship between indicators and their constructs) is specified. The result is that the residual variance of the independent variables (both latent and indicator variables) minimize.

B. Research Sample

Fig. 3: Research Framework

Source: Primary Data, 2022

X_1 = Product Quality
 X_2 = Brand Image
 X_3 = After sales services
 Z = Purchase Decision (Intervening)
 Y = Customer Satisfaction

not have a high correlation. If the correlation value of the construct with the measurement item is greater than the correlation value with other constructs, then it shows that the latent construct predicts the size of their block better than the size of the other blocks, and it said that the construct has high discriminant validity (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). The following are the results of discriminant validity from the cross-loading value between the indicators and their respective constructs:

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

• Data Analysis Results

Discriminant Validity is a measurement that has the principle that the measurement of different constructs does

INDIKATOR	KUALITAS PRODUK	CITRA MEREK	LAYANAN PURNA JUAL	KEPUTUSAN PEMBELIAN	KEPUASAN PELANGGAN
KP1	0.688	0.288	0.346	0.368	0.447
KP2	0.732	0.338	0.377	0.454	0.432
KP3	0.731	0.305	0.391	0.399	0.352
KP4	0.696	0.344	0.372	0.338	0.434
KP5	0.685	0.355	0.351	0.349	0.361
KP6	0.712	0.321	0.326	0.395	0.351
CM1	0.472	0.749	0.594	0.502	0.539
CM2	0.27	0.779	0.62	0.57	0.529
CM3	0.242	0.72	0.749	0.583	0.507
CM4	0.391	0.757	0.592	0.654	0.685
LPJ1	0.242	0.72	0.749	0.583	0.507
LPJ2	0.354	0.647	0.791	0.671	0.549
LPJ3	0.434	0.603	0.691	0.544	0.531
LPJ4	0.429	0.571	0.721	0.573	0.537
LPJ5	0.338	0.664	0.769	0.647	0.616
LPJ6	0.484	0.612	0.74	0.584	0.599
LPJ7	0.349	0.544	0.691	0.479	0.501
KPB1	0.453	0.579	0.603	0.741	0.6
KPB2	0.381	0.543	0.575	0.708	0.526
KPB3	0.388	0.608	0.637	0.765	0.644
KPB4	0.319	0.64	0.623	0.733	0.573
KPB5	0.348	0.529	0.586	0.746	0.518
KPB6	0.448	0.527	0.571	0.687	0.562
KPB7	0.393	0.488	0.461	0.699	0.585
KPB8	0.434	0.573	0.557	0.732	0.616
KPL1	0.41	0.373	0.511	0.479	0.522
KPL2	0.437	0.625	0.607	0.618	0.804
KPL3	0.381	0.547	0.496	0.58	0.715
KPL4	0.467	0.593	0.602	0.605	0.799
KPL5	0.425	0.62	0.538	0.609	0.781
KPL6	0.326	0.517	0.49	0.568	0.693

Table 2: Cross Loading

Source: Smart PLS Data Processing

Based on table 2, the correlation value of the construct with its indicators is greater than the correlation value with other constructs. Discriminant validity testing looks at the

AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value. Discriminant validity serves to measure the accuracy of the reflective model. The AVE value of Discriminant validity is that if the

AVE value is less than 0.5, it is declared invalid, while if the AVE value is more significant than 0.5, then it is declared

valid (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). The following are the values from the AVE table.

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Score	Remarks
Kualitas Produk	0.501	>0.5	Valid
Citra Merek	0.565	>0.5	Valid
Layanan Purna Jual	0.543	>0.5	Valid
Keputusan Pembelian	0.528	>0.5	Valid
Kepuasan Pelanggan	0.526	>0.5	Valid

Table 3: Discriminant Validity AVE (Average Variance Extracted) Results

Source: Smart PLS Data Processing

The validity test where Convergent Validity, discriminant validity, cross-loading, and AVE values can be declared to have good test criteria because the research model is acceptable (valid). They are testing the structural model with PLS, looking at the R-Square value for each endogenous latent variable as the predictive power of the

structural model. Changes in the value of R-Square can explain the effect of certain exogenous latent variables on whether endogenous latent variables have an effect. R-Square values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 that the model is robust, moderate, and weak (Ghozali and Latan, 2015).

Construct	R-Square
Purchase Decision	0.686
Customer Satisfaction	0.701

Table 4: Value of R²

Source: Smart PLS Data Processing

Based on table 4, the R-Square value of 0.686 indicated the variability of the purchase decision construct, which variability of the construct of product quality, brand image, and after-sales service is 68.6% while other variables outside the research explain 31.4%. Based on this, the results of the calculation of R2 show that the value is

excellent and robust. Then the R-Square value of 0.701 of the purchasing decision construct is 70.1%. Based on this, the results of the calculation of R2 show that the value is excellent and robust. The results of hypothesis testing can be seen in table 5 below.

Relationships Between Constructs	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	TStatistic (O/STDEV)	P Values
Product Quality -> Purchase Decision	0.175	0.177	0.054	3.251	0.001
Brand Image -> Purchase Decision	0.339	0.336	0.076	4.482	0.000
After Sales Service -> Purchase Decision	0.419	0.425	0.085	4.954	0.000
Purchase Decision -> Customer Satisfaction	0.415	0.413	0.068	6.08	0.000
Product Quality -> Customer Satisfaction	0.158	0.159	0.051	3.099	0.002
Brand Image -> Customer Satisfaction	0.291	0.295	0.087	3.329	0.001
After Sales Service -> Customer Satisfaction	0.09	0.088	0.094	0.959	0.338
Product Quality -> Purchase Decision -> Customer Satisfaction	0.073	0.073	0.022	3.235	0.001
Brand Image -> Purchase Decision -> Customer Satisfaction	0.141	0.141	0.037	3.763	0.0000
After Sales Service -> Purchase Decision -> Customer Satisfaction	0.174	0.177	0.051	3.402	0.001

Table 5: Path Coefficients

Source: Smart PLS Data Processing

Based on the results of hypothesis testing in this study, the researchers found a positive and significant effect of product quality on purchasing decisions. These results by research from Waluya et al. (2019), product quality has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions. This study also follows Amron's (2018) research that product quality positively and significantly affects purchasing decisions.

Researchers found a positive and significant influence of brand image on purchasing decisions. These results are the same as the results studied by Joghee and Dube (2018) that there is a positive and significant influence on the brand image on purchasing decisions. These results are under research conducted by Nga et al. (2019), brand image has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions.

The results of hypothesis testing in this study found that there was a positive and significant influence on after-sales service on purchasing decisions. According to the research conducted by Abdullah and Fejza (2020), after-sales service has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions. In addition, this research is supported by research researched by Syukur et al. (2020), namely after-sales service has a positive and significant influence on decisions. Azizah's (2020) research result was that purchasing decisions have a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. Product quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction.

These results follow research conducted by Pradita and Sitio (2020) that brand image has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. Based on the results of this study, there was a positive effect of after-sales service on customer satisfaction.

Product quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction mediated by purchasing decisions. Heryanto (2017) stated that product quality has a significant influence on customer satisfaction mediated by purchasing decisions. Researchers found a positive and significant effect of brand image on customer satisfaction mediated by purchasing decisions. Azizah's (2020) research result stated that brand image positively influences customer satisfaction mediated by purchasing decisions. In addition, there is a positive and significant effect of after-sales service on customer satisfaction which is mediated by purchasing decisions. This result is the same as the results studied by Pradita and Sitio (2020) that there is a positive and significant effect of after-sales service on customer satisfaction mediated by purchasing decisions.

V. CONCLUSION

Product quality has a positive and significant influence on Toyota's car purchasing decisions. A car with a powerful engine performance so that the engine is not easily damaged when used can affect consumers in purchasing decisions. The higher the quality of the product provided by the manufacturer, the more the product quality becomes one of the considerations in making purchasing decisions for

Toyota cars.

Brand image has a positive and significant influence on Toyota car purchase decisions. When it is a car brand, the brand will always be in the minds of consumers, so that when consumers are going to buy a car, the brand is the first in the consumer's mind when they want to choose a car, so that it can make consumers make purchasing decisions if the car brand is easy to remember, so that it can make consumers make a purchasing decision on Toyota cars.

After-sales service has a positive and significant influence on Toyota car purchase decisions. The company does a good service if the car is damaged during the period of use by responding quickly and responsively when consumers make warranty claims for the car so that this can influence consumers in making decisions to buy Toyota cars. Suppose the company responds to warranty claims quickly to make consumers make a purchasing decision on Toyota cars.

Purchase decisions positively and significantly impact customer satisfaction for Toyota cars. Before making a purchase decision, consumers first evaluate alternatively by comparing the prices of each car brand so that the competitive price of Toyota cars can make customers satisfied. Purchasing decisions will increase if car prices are more competitive, making Toyota car customers feel satisfied.

Product quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. A car that has good performance is a car that has a powerful engine performance so that the engine is not easily damaged when used frequently; the more durable the Toyota engine is, the more satisfied customers will be with Toyota cars.

Brand image has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. When a car brand has a good image because the ability of the product follows what is expected by consumers, the brand will always be in the minds of consumers so that it can make customers satisfied with Toyota cars, because the image Toyota's brand is in line with what customers want.

After-sales service has a positive influence on customer satisfaction. Suppose the customer submits a warranty claim during the period of use. In that case, they are using a fast and responsive response when the consumer makes a warranty claim on the car to affect customer satisfaction with Toyota cars. After all, it follows the customer's wishes because processing claims can do it quickly and easily.

Product quality has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction, mediated by purchasing decisions. For purchasing decisions in choosing a car, namely, a car that has good performance is a car that has a powerful engine performance so that the engine is not easily damaged when used frequently.

Brand image has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction, mediated by purchasing decisions.

For purchasing decisions in choosing a car, namely, because the car brand can make customers feel satisfied with Toyota cars because they follow what customers want. Brand image has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction, mediated by purchasing decisions. For purchasing decisions in choosing a car, it can be seen from the service from the company when responding to warranty claims for damaged cars owned by customers. So a good company is a company that provides good service if damaged during use, by responding quickly and responsibly when consumers make warranty claims on the car so that it can affect customer satisfaction with Toyota cars.

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